

1st MOMENT - FOCAL GROUP
QUESTIONS RELATED TO CURRENT RECORDS

- 1) How does the process of communication and collaboration between a medical team occur through current medical records, both in paper and electronic?
- 2) How is information from different parties and organizations integrated?
- 3) How does the patient currently manage their health information issued by different entities?
- 4) How does patient access control occur in current electronic medical records?

2nd MOMENT - FOCAL GROUP
QUESTIONS RELATED TO COLLABORATIVE CONSTRUCTIONS

4C COLLABORATION MODEL

- 1) How could the proposed solution increase the quality of a collaborative investigation concerning a patient's diagnosis?
- 2) What critical aspects about communication between professionals could it be possible to mitigate with the use of the proposed solution?
- 3) How important do you consider the possibility of access control in sharing and managing your records with other participants?

BLOCKCHAIN-BASED EPR

- 4) How can the issue of data privacy and patient access control be perceived through the proposed solution used?
- 5) What can the immutability of medical records using the blockchain guarantee concerning the audit of data reported by health entities?
- 6) The use of blockchain enables the availability of information, that is, medical records can be accessed at any time. What is your perception of this feature?